

Polarographic Studies on Complexation Behaviour of 2,3-Dihydroxypyridine with some First Transition Metal Cations in Aqueous Ethanol (50%) Media

SANJAY SENGUPTA, N. R. BANERJEE* and D. P. GOEL

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

Manuscript received 26 October 1987, revised 1 June 1988, accepted 29 July 1988

Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method applied to diffusion currents of the complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with 2,3-dihydroxypyridine has yielded the following $\log K$, and $\log K_s$ values (298 K): Mn^{II} , 4.40, 3.18; Co^{II} , 4.78, 3.17; Ni^{II} , 5.50, 3.65; Cu^{II} , 7.67, 3.16; Zn^{II} , 3.82, 3.78. The overall stability constant values have also been calculated by least-square method. The order of overall stability constants follow Irving-Williams natural order. The ΔG , ΔH and ΔS values determined from data for 288, 298 and 308 K are found to be all negative, proving the formation of strong complexes with greater order in the complex molecules.

2,3-Dihydroxypyridine, as a bidentate ligand, are used for spectrophotometric determination of Fe^{III} and UO_2^{II} ions¹. It has been also used for potentiometric determination of stabilities of complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} cations¹. In the present communication, the results of polarographic studies on the complex formation of this ligand have been described. Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method^{2,3} applied to diffusion currents for increasing concentration of complexes in solution (50% aqueous ethanol) has been employed to calculate the stability constants. Similar studies at three different temperatures (288, 298 and 308 K) have been made to calculate the thermodynamic parameters of the complexes.

Experimental

2,3-Dihydroxypyridine (Aldrich), lithium hydroxide (C.D.H., India), manganese, cobalt and zinc oxides, nickel(II) and copper(II) nitrates and perchloric acid (all E. Merck) and aldehyde-free ethanol were used. The oxides and nitrates were converted to perchlorates with perchloric acid, care being taken to boil off nitric acid in the cases of nitrates before crystallisation.

Radiometer PO4g polarograph at a chart speed of 2 cm min^{-1} , Sargent capillary, with characteristics $m=1.068$ mg s^{-1} and $t=4.3$ s for 70 cm/Hg head, Julabo F-40-HC (West Germany) circulating cooling thermostat, IOLAR grade I (Indian Oxygen) nitrogen gas, Elico LI-120 digital pH-meter and Kalousek type double-walled cell were used for recording the polarograms.

The test solutions comprised (a) metal ClO_4 (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm^{-3}), $LiClO_4$ (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm^{-3}), ethanol (5 ml), gelatin (1.0 ml, 0.05%) made upto 10 ml with double-distilled water, and (b)

metal ClO_4 (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm^{-3}), $LiClO_4$ (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm^{-3}), gelatin (1.0 ml, 0.05%) increasing volumes of 2,3-dihydroxypyridine in ethanol (0.01 mmol dm^{-3}), additional ethanol to make up the ethanol content to 5 ml and double-distilled water to make upto 10 ml. pH of the solutions were adjusted to appropriate values, as given in the respective tables.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic and derived data are presented in Tables 1-5. The well-defined diffusion-controlled cathodic waves have slopes of about 50 mV for the two-electron process. Since $\Delta E_{1/2}$ values for these quasi-reversible waves cannot be used to determine the stability constants, Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method has been used. For this purpose, changes in diffusion currents (Δi_d) in the presence of increasing concentration of the ligand have been plotted against logarithm of ligand concentration, $\log[L]$ and the sigmoidal pseudo-formation curves⁴⁻⁶ have been integrated to obtain a set of $\log F'_0[L]$ values. Plots of $\log F'_0[L]$ values vs $\log[L]$ give from the limiting slope and n_{max} ($=2$), the proportionality constant k between $\bar{n}$ and Δi_d values. This is then used to obtain $\log F_0[L]$ from the $\log F'_0[L]$ values. Plots of $F_0[L]$ vs $\log[L]$ give then $F_1[L]$ values and those of $F_1[L]$ vs $\log[L]$ the $F_2[L]$ values and so on⁶. The results of analysis of data at 298 K have been given in Tables 1-5.

The stability constants have also been computed using least-square programme patterned after Sullivan *et al.*⁷ and the values are given in Table 6 in parenthesis. It is evident from Tables 1-5 that the overall stability constants ($\log \beta_n$) of the complexes follow the order proposed by Mellor-Maley⁸ and Irving-Williams^{9,10}: $Mn < Co < Ni$

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC AND OTHER DATA FOR Mn-2,3-DIHYDROXYPYRIDINE COMPLEXES (pH=6.4) IN ETHANOL-WATER (50%) MEDIA

Temp. = 298 K, Mn^{II} ion concn. = 0.1 mol dm⁻³

[L] mol dm ⁻³	-E _{1/2} V	i _d μA	Δi _d μA	log F _o	log F _o	F _o	F ₁ × 10 ⁻³	F ₂ × 10 ⁻³
0.000 00	1.34	3.26	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.000 01	1.36	3.21	0.05	0.022 3	0.138 8	1.377	—	—
0.000 05	1.38	3.19	0.07	0.057 8	0.860 8	2.293	25.860	172
0.000 1	1.40	3.15	0.11	0.107 8	0.668 2	4.658	36.530	1 158
0.000 5	1.42	3.13	0.13	0.218 4	1.360 1	22.920	43.840	377
0.001 0	1.44	3.11	0.15	0.389 8	1.804 8	63.800	62.800	378
0.002 0	1.46	3.08	0.18	0.882 8	2.380 9	240 400	119 700	1 677
0.005 0	1.47	3.04	0.22	0.509 9	3.175 6	1 498 000	299 400	2 946

log K₁ = 4.40, log K₂ = 3.18, log β₃ = 7.58.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC AND OTHER DATA FOR Co-2,3-DIHYDROXYPYRIDINE COMPLEXES (pH=7.0) IN ETHANOL-WATER (50%) MEDIA

Temp. = 298 K, Co^{II} ion concn. = 0.1 mmol dm⁻³

[L] mol dm ⁻³	-E _{1/2} V	i _d μA	Δi _d μA	log F _o	log F _o	F _o	F ₁ × 10 ⁻³	F ₂ × 10 ⁻³
0 000 00	1.31	1.08	—	—	—	—	—	—
0 000 01	1.34	0.94	0.14	0.065 5	0.263 3	1.333	—	—
0.000 05	1.36	0.90	0.18	0.160 5	0.645 2	4.418	66.360	127.2
0.000 1	1.38	0.86	0.22	0.243 0	0.976 8	9.479	84.790	249.0
0.000 5	1.39	0.80	0.28	0.429 5	1.726 5	53.260	104.520	89.0
0.001 0	1.40	0.78	0.30	0.541 5	2.176 8	150.300	149.300	89.3
0.002 0	1.42	0.76	0.32	0.718 0	2.886 3	769.600	384.300	162.0
0.005 0	1.43	0.70	0.38	0.916 0	3 632 3	4 811 000	962.000	181.0

log K₁ = 4.78, log K₂ = 3.17, log β₃ = 7.95.

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC AND OTHER DATA FOR Ni-2,3-DIHYDROXYPYRIDINE COMPLEXES (pH=6.8) IN ETHANOL-WATER (50%) MEDIA

Temp. = 298 K, Ni^{II} ion concn. = 0.1 mmol dm⁻³

[L] mol dm ⁻³	-E _{1/2} V	i _d μA	Δi _d μA	log F _o	log F _o	F _o	F ₁ × 10 ⁻³	F ₂ × 10 ⁻³
0.000 00	1.10	1.60	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.000 01	1.12	1.53	0.07	0.056 7	0.642 4	4.389	323.900	189
0.000 03	1.14	1.52	0.08	0.099 2	1.123 9	13.300	410.000	800
0.000 1	1.16	1.51	0.09	0.147 3	1 668 9	46.650	456.600	137
0.000 5	1.18	1.44	0.16	0.239 6	2 714 6	518.100	1 034.200	143
0.001 0	1.20	1.42	0.18	0.286 8	3.247 1	1 766.000	1 765.000	144
0.002 0	1.22	1.38	0.22	0.437 8	4.960 2	91 200 000	45 995 000	2 283
0.005 0	1.24	1.37	0.23	0.506 6	5.739 7	549 200.000	109 839.300	2 190

log K₁ = 5.50, log K₂ = 3.65, log β₃ = 9.15.

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC AND OTHER DATA FOR Cu-2,3-DIHYDROXYPYRIDINE COMPLEXES (pH=5.4) IN ETHANOL-WATER (50%) MEDIA

Temp. = 298 K, Cu^{II} ion concn. = 0.1 mmol dm⁻³

[L] mol dm ⁻³	-E _{1/2} V	i _d μA	Δi _d μA	log F _o	log F _o	F _o × 10 ⁻³	F ₁ × 10 ⁻³	F ₂ × 10 ⁻³
0.000 00	0.12	3.84	—	—	—	—	—	—
0 000 01	0.14	2.34	1.50	2.499 0	2.611 4	408.7	40.77	2 633.3
0.000 03	0.16	2.26	1.58	3.079 0	3.217 5	1 648.0	54.90	680
0.000 5	0.18	2.08	1.76	4.409 0	4.607 4	40 500.0	80.99	678
0.000 75	0.20	2.04	1.80	4.659 0	4.868 5	73 870.0	98.49	686
0.001 0	0.22	2.00	1.84	5 479 0	5 725 5	531 400.0	531.39	4 843
0.001 5	0.23	1.84	2.00	6.459 0	6.749 6	5 618 000.0	3 745.33	2 466.6
0.005 0	0.24	1.80	2.04	7.459 0	7.794 6	62 270 000.0	12 453.99	24 812.0

log K₁ = 7.67, log K₂ = 3.16, log β₃ = 10.83.

TABLE 5—POLAROGRAPHIC AND OTHER DATA FOR Zn-2,3-DIHYDROXYPYRIDINE COMPLEXES (pH=5.4) IN ETHANOL-WATER (50%) MEDIA

 Temp.=298 K, Zn^{II} ion concn.=0.1 mmol dm⁻³

[L] mol dm ⁻³	-E _{1/2} V	i _d μA	Δi _d μA	log F ₀	log F ₀	F ₀	F ₁ × 10 ⁻³	F ₂ × 10 ⁻⁴
0.000 00	1.20	2.06	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.000 01	1.22	1.88	0.18	0.080 9	0.202 2	1.593	—	—
0.000 03	1.24	1.84	0.22	0.185 9	0.464 7	2.911	—	—
0.000 5	1.26	1.82	0.24	0.300 4	0.751 0	5.636	92.72	5 844
0.001 0	1.28	1.80	0.26	0.431 9	1.099 7	12.560	115.60	4 960
0.002 0	1.30	1.79	0.27	0.573 4	1.433 5	27.100	130.50	3 230
0.003 0	1.32	1.76	0.30	0.723 4	1.808 5	64.270	210.90	4 830
0.005 0	1.34	1.70	0.36	0.900 9	2.252 2	178.700	355.40	5 790

 log K₁=3.82, log K₂=3.78, log β₂=7.60.

TABLE 6—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE METAL COMPLEXES WITH 2,3-DIHYDROXYPYRIDINE

Metal ion	Overall stability constants*			25° (°C)		
	15°	25°	35°	-ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Mn ^{II}	8.06 (8.08)	7.57 (7.59)	7.33 (7.34)	43.222	69.816	-69.10
Co ^{II}	8.15 (8.16)	7.94 (7.93)	7.66 (7.64)	52.227	57.441	-17.49
Ni ^{II}	9.18 (9.17)	9.15 (9.14)	8.76 (8.74)	45.358	44.669	-4.89
Cu ^{II}	11.06 (11.05)	10.83 (10.81)	10.05 (10.04)	61.805	76.588	-49.60
Zn ^{II}	8.02 (8.03)	7.60 (7.63)	7.27 (7.28)	43.365	51.058	-25.81

*Least-square values in parenthesis.

< Cu > Zn. From the slopes of the Arrhenius plots (log β₂ vs 1/T) for the complexes of 2,3-dihydroxypyridine at three different temperatures, the ΔH values have been computed (Table 6). The ΔS values have then been obtained from Gibbs-Helmholtz relationship. The results indicate that ΔG is negative, showing spontaneous formation of the complexes. The enthalpy of formation of M(II)-2,3-dihydroxypyridine (1:2) systems are also highly negative which makes the complex molecules attain higher order than hydrated metal ions.

References

- D. P. GOEL, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Delhi, 1969.
- D. R. CROW, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1963, 28, 1799.
- D. R. CROW, *Talanta*, 1962, 29, 733.
- D. R. CROW, "Polarography of Metal Complexes", Academic, New York, 1969, p. 100.
- D. R. CROW, *Talanta*, 1962, 29, 739.
- I. LEDEN, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, 188, 160.
- J. O. SULLIVAN, J. RYDBERG and W. E. MILLER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, 13, 2023.
- D. P. MELLOR and L. E. MALEY, *Nature (London)*, 1947, 159, 370.
- H. M. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3, 92.
- H. M. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature (London)*, 1948, 162, 746.